

Partial-Label Evaluation of Prototype Components with Temporal Aggregation

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Abstract

Offline evaluation sets for bioacoustic classification often cover only a subset of the species present at deployment. This creates a model-selection risk for interpretable components: a prototype head may appear useful on the covered species while scoring lower after full-system deployment, including for species the offline benchmark cannot evaluate. We study this failure mode in a 234-species multi-taxon soundscape deployment testbed built from frozen Perch embeddings, a prototype member, a sound-event-detection member, and rank fusion. The deployed prototype member uses temporal aggregation across soundscape windows, while the primary replacement heads make window-level predictions. On a 708-window labelled soundscape bank covering 71 of 234 species, the replacement heads form an interpretability–accuracy frontier, and the higher-accuracy D2 head outperforms the deployed prototype member on the covered-species offline endpoint. However, this offline selection signal is not mirrored in hidden-test deployment: D1 scores 0.938 private macro-AUC, D2 scores 0.937, and a raw-Perch version without the prototype member scores 0.939, while the deployed temporally aggregated prototype member remains best at 0.942. Exploratory diagnostics compare covered and offline-absent species, and a no-SSM ablation reduces the deployed head from 0.94218 to 0.94089 private macro-AUC. This ablation reports the score change after bypassing one temporal module but does not identify the full causal mechanism. A supporting matched-control study shows that prototype explanations can be class-pure and call-focused in a cleaner setting, so the result is not simply a failure of prototypes as explanations. Overall, our experiments provide a scoped descriptive case study of partial-label evaluation: a prototype component can improve a covered-species offline benchmark while failing to improve the full bioacoustic deployment system.

Keywords

Bioacoustics, Prototype Components, Temporal Aggregation, Partial-Label Evaluation, Offline-Deployment Gap, Model Selection

1. Introduction

Bioacoustic deployment systems often operate over a broader label space than the labels available for local offline evaluation. This mismatch is especially important for interpretable components. A prototype head may improve an offline benchmark on the species that happen to be labelled, while reducing performance for deployment species the offline bank never evaluates. The resulting failure is not simply a low-score problem: it is a model-selection problem, where a component can appear better under a partial-label endpoint and worse inside the full system.

We study this problem using the BirdCLEF+ 2026 challenge [1], part of LifeCLEF 2026 [2], as a concrete deployment testbed. The task requires identifying 234 bird, amphibian, insect, mammal, and reptile species from Brazilian Pantanal soundscape recordings under a 90-minute CPU-only inference budget. It extends the BirdCLEF series from bird-only classification toward broader passive-acoustic biodiversity monitoring [3, 4]. This setting introduces several practical challenges:

- Significant domain shift between focal training recordings and passive-acoustic-monitoring soundscapes [5];
- Severe class imbalance, with some common species having hundreds of recordings and rare species having fewer than ten;
- Partial label coverage in offline soundscape evaluation, where the labelled soundscape bank used in this work contains positives for only 71 of 234 target species;

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- Incomplete foundation-model coverage, with 28 of 234 species lacking Perch [6] logit mappings.

Many strong bioacoustic competition systems address these constraints by combining pretrained audio models, prototype or embedding-based components, sound-event-detection models, rank fusion, and post-processing. In this work, we use a fixed ProtoSSMv2+SED rank-fusion core, implemented from public Kaggle reference notebooks [7], as a deployment testbed. This fixed core scored 0.942 private macro-AUC. We hold the core fixed and replace only its prototype member with author-built prototype heads trained on frozen Perch embeddings.

This controlled replacement setup lets us study a specific evaluation question: when prototype components are evaluated offline on a partially covered soundscape bank, does the offline model-selection signal transfer when the component is deployed inside the full label space? The question is especially relevant because the deployed prototype member uses temporal aggregation across soundscape windows, whereas our primary replacement heads are simpler window-level prototype models. Thus, the comparison tests not only prototype-head design, but also whether a window-level offline endpoint is sufficient for selecting a temporally aggregated component inside a full deployment system.

The observed replacement results show a mismatch between the offline endpoint and hidden-test deployment in this setting. On the 708-window labelled soundscape bank covering 71 species, the author-built heads form an interpretability-accuracy frontier, and the higher-accuracy D2 head exceeds the deployed prototype member on the covered-species offline endpoint. However, when the heads are swapped into the full system and scored on the hidden test, neither primary replacement improves over dropping the prototype member for raw Perch logits. D1 scores 0.938 private, D2 scores 0.937, raw Perch scores 0.939, and the deployed temporally aggregated prototype member remains best at 0.942. Exploratory diagnostics then compare covered and offline-absent species, and a no-SSM ablation reduces the deployed head to 0.94089 private macro-AUC. This ablation records the score change after bypassing one temporal module but does not isolate the full causal mechanism.

Our contributions are:

- A controlled system-level replacement protocol that swaps only the prototype member of a fixed Perch+prototype+SED rank-fusion pipeline;
- An offline interpretability-accuracy frontier for author-built prototype heads trained on frozen Perch embeddings;
- Hidden-test evidence that the offline selection signal is not mirrored by the full deployment label space;
- Exploratory diagnostics comparing behavior on species covered by, and absent from, the offline soundscape bank;
- A temporal-module ablation that reports the hidden-test score after bypassing the deployed member’s SSM-based aggregation.

A supporting matched-control study shows that prototype explanations can be class-pure and call-focused in a cleaner setting. We therefore do not interpret the observed deployment mismatch as a general failure of prototype explanations. Instead, we frame it as a failure mode of partial-label evaluation for interpretable components in bioacoustic deployment systems.

2. Related Work

2.1. Prototype networks and interpretability

Prototype networks aim to make classification decisions interpretable by comparing an input to learned representative examples. ProtoPNet [8] introduced this paradigm for image classification: a convolutional backbone extracts latent features, a prototype layer measures similarity to learned class-specific prototypes, and the final layer maps prototype activations to class predictions. This produces a “this

looks like that” form of explanation in which the prototypes are part of the model rather than a post-hoc visualization.

However, prototype interpretability is not automatic. Prior work has shown that latent prototype similarity may fail to correspond to meaningful input-space similarity, especially when prototypes capture artifacts or compressed features rather than semantically relevant structure [9]. This motivates evaluating prototype quality quantitatively rather than relying only on visual or acoustic examples. In this work, we measure prototype validity using class purity and shortcut rate in a matched-control setting, and then test whether prototype components that look strong offline remain useful inside a deployed bioacoustic system.

2.2. Prototype and foundation models in bioacoustics

AudioProtoPNet [10] adapts the prototype-network paradigm to multi-label bird sound classification, using a ConvNeXt backbone pretrained on BirdSet [11]. It shows that prototype explanations can be useful in bird-only bioacoustic classification, but leaves broader multi-taxon settings as future work. Our supporting matched-control study probes this boundary by testing whether prototype explanations remain class-pure and call-focused in a cleaner audio setting before studying their failure inside the full multi-taxon deployment system.

Pretrained bioacoustic models have become central to recent BirdCLEF systems. BirdNET [12], Perch [6], PANNs [13], and BirdSet backbones [11] provide strong feature extractors for downstream classification. In BirdCLEF+ 2026, we use frozen Perch embeddings and logits as the fixed representation layer for all prototype-head replacement experiments. This lets us study the prototype component itself while holding the backbone representation constant.

2.3. Bioacoustic systems and component-level evaluation

Recent BirdCLEF working notes emphasize transfer learning, pseudo-labeling, distillation, ensembling, and post-processing as practical tools for bioacoustic classification under domain shift and strict inference budgets. Miyaguchi et al. [14] explored lightweight tokenized spectrogram embeddings for fast inference, while Sydorskyi and Gonçalves [15] used semi-supervised distillation and iterative pseudo-labeling to achieve a private AUC of 0.928 in BirdCLEF+ 2025. These studies report system-level performance and ablations, but they do not focus on whether an offline selection signal for an interpretable component transfers when that component is inserted into the full deployment system.

This component-versus-system question is important for BirdCLEF+ 2026 because offline soundscape evaluation may cover only part of the deployment label space. In our case, the labelled soundscape bank used for offline prototype evaluation contains positives for only 71 of 234 target species. A prototype head can therefore improve the covered-species offline benchmark while reducing performance on species the offline bank cannot evaluate. Our work studies this failure mode directly by replacing only the prototype member of a fixed Perch+prototype+SED rank-fusion pipeline, measuring the effect on the hidden 234-species leaderboard, and adding a temporal-module ablation as a sensitivity check on the deployed member’s SSM-based aggregation.

3. Task and Data

3.1. Task overview

BirdCLEF+ 2026 [1] targets 234 species from the Brazilian Pantanal, expanding beyond previous editions’ bird-only scope [3, 4]. Participants predict species-presence probabilities for each 5-second window of one-minute soundscape recordings. The evaluation metric is macro-averaged ROC-AUC, skipping classes with no true positives in the test set¹. All inference must complete within a 90-minute CPU-only budget on a Kaggle notebook (Intel Xeon, 4 cores).

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/code/metric/birdclef-roc-auc>

Table 1

Species distribution and approximate focal recording counts by taxon. Perch mapping coverage is reported separately in the text because the mapping artifact includes both direct and proxy mappings.

Taxon	Species	Focal rec.
Aves	162	~24,000
Amphibia	35	~1,800
Insecta	28	~900
Mammalia	8	~300
Reptilia	1	~20
Total	234	~27,000

3.2. Competition data and species distribution

Table 1 summarizes the dataset composition. Training data includes focal recordings from three sources: Xeno-Canto², iNaturalist³, and the Colombian Sound Archive (CSA). Labelled soundscapes with 5-second multi-label annotations are also provided. Class imbalance is severe: the most-represented bird species have hundreds of recordings, while several mammal and insect species have fewer than 10. This imbalance motivates the partial-label evaluation problem studied here: the offline soundscape bank used for prototype development covers only 71 of 234 species with positive instances.

3.3. Domain shift

The core difficulty is a focal→soundscape domain shift, well-documented in prior BirdCLEF editions [15]. Focal recordings are clean, single-species clips recorded at close range with directional microphones. Soundscapes are captured by passive acoustic monitoring devices, contain overlapping species (approximately 4.2 per positive window), background noise from rain and wind, and varying recording conditions (Figure 1).

This shift provides deployment context for our experiments. The analyses below focus specifically on the interaction between partial offline label coverage and full-system deployment, rather than treating domain shift alone as the explanation.

3.4. Perch coverage gap

A separate coverage issue comes from the Perch class mapping. Of the 234 target species, 206 have a Perch logit mapping in the released mapping artifact, including proxy mappings, and 28 produce no Perch logit signal. The unmapped species are concentrated mainly among insects and amphibians.

This Perch coverage gap is distinct from the offline evaluation gap. The Perch gap concerns which species receive foundation-model logit support, whereas the offline evaluation gap concerns which species have positive labels in the 708-window soundscape bank. In our offline bank, only 71 of 234 species have positive examples; the remaining 163 species cannot contribute to offline macro-AUC. Section 7 analyzes how this partial offline coverage relates to the hidden-test replacement results.

3.5. Offline soundscape bank and split construction

For local prototype development and offline evaluation, we use a labelled soundscape bank drawn from the competition-provided 5-second multi-label soundscape annotations. A one-minute source file is included only when all twelve annotated 5-second windows are present; seven incomplete files are excluded. This yields 708 windows from 59 one-minute source files. Perch embeddings and logits are materialized for the resulting bank in the analysis pipeline. We do not rebalance the bank by species or taxon.

²<https://xeno-canto.org/>

³<https://www.inaturalist.org/>

Focal → soundscape domain shift (same species)

Figure 1: Focal→soundscape domain shift for one species (Dwarf Tree Frog). Panel A/top shows a clean, single-species focal recording; Panel B/bottom shows a labelled 5-second soundscape window containing the same species plus eight annotated overlapping species and environmental noise. Both panels are dB-scaled spectrograms on the same time and frequency axes and the same displayed colour scale. This pair is illustrative rather than a quantitative summary of all recordings and is not used as a quantitative endpoint.

The target population for this bank is the competition-provided labelled soundscape subset of the BirdCLEF+ 2026 task, not the full hidden-test distribution. The bank is an availability sample: we use all complete one-minute labelled soundscape files available to the local analysis after excluding incomplete files, rather than selecting files by a power calculation or taxon-balanced sampling plan. The resulting sample size is therefore a property of the released labelled soundscape annotations; it is sufficient for a development endpoint but not for a powered species-level deployment test.

All offline folds are constructed at the source-file level using GroupKFold(5), with the one-minute filename as the grouping variable and no shuffling. Five folds are used to keep validation units at the source-file level while leaving roughly a dozen one-minute files in each held-out split; this is a pragmatic leakage-control choice, not a power calculation. In each fold, all windows from a given one-minute source file are assigned entirely to either the training split or the held-out split; no windows from the same source file cross the train-validation boundary. The five held-out fold sizes are 144, 144, 144, 144, and 132 windows, corresponding to 12, 12, 12, 12, and 11 source files. Species are included in offline macro-AUC only if they have at least one positive instance in the 708-window bank, yielding 71 evaluable species. The remaining 163 target species have no positive examples in this bank, so the offline endpoint can evaluate covered-species behavior but cannot directly evaluate behavior on absent species. The exact covered and absent species lists are released with the artifact snapshot as

results/covered_species_71.csv and results/absent_species_163.csv.

The primary D1 and D2 replacement heads and the offline design sweeps in Tables 5–7 are developed on this soundscape bank. Focal recordings are not used to train the primary D1 and D2 heads; they are introduced only in the separate D2-FOCAL sensitivity experiment (Section 7). Thus, the main offline endpoint and the primary replacement heads share the same labelled soundscape source, while the hidden leaderboard provides a separate system-level deployment check.

3.6. Evaluation endpoints and analysis plan

We distinguish component-level offline evaluation from system-level deployment evaluation. The single primary deployment endpoint is aggregate Kaggle private macro-AUC for the hidden-test replacement comparison against the deployed ProtoSSMv2 reference. The offline OOF macro-AUC endpoint is used for replacement-head development and selection, not as the final deployment endpoint. The primary hypothesis is directional and descriptive: if the partial-label offline endpoint is a reliable model-selection signal for the full system, then the prototype component favored by covered-species offline macro-AUC should also improve hidden-test deployment performance when inserted into the fixed deployment core. The primary offline analysis population is the 71 covered species in the 708-window soundscape bank. The primary deployment analysis population is the full 234-species hidden-test task, available only through aggregate public/private leaderboard macro-AUC.

The model-selection rule is fixed before inspecting the hidden-test replacement outcomes: D2 is the high-offline-AUC replacement selected from the local sweeps, D1 is the high-purity pure-prototype comparison, and Drop is the no-prototype baseline. The primary deployment comparison is the private macro-AUC of ProtoSSMv2, Drop, D1 pure, and D2 input-gated after inserting each prototype artifact into the same ProtoSSMv2+SED core. Transfer is judged descriptively by whether the offline-selected replacement improves over the deployed ProtoSSMv2 reference or at least over the Drop baseline in the full system.

For the offline replacement sweeps, the comparison framework is descriptive: we compare point estimates of concatenated out-of-fold macro-AUC over the 71 covered species and use prototype presence-purity as a secondary interpretability descriptor. D2 is selected by the largest covered-species OOF macro-AUC among the author-built replacement heads, whereas D1 is retained as the high-purity pure-prototype comparison. We do not use a significance test, alpha threshold, or multiple-comparison correction to select D1 or D2 from the development sweeps.

All other analyses are exploratory diagnostics or sensitivity checks. Coverage-gating, re-weighting, D2-FOCAL, per-taxon breakdowns, absent-species diagnostics, temporal ablation, and the supporting AudioProtoPNet matched-control study are not confirmatory endpoints; they are used to describe candidate mechanisms and boundary conditions. Because the local bank is small and the hidden-test labels are unavailable, we present the paper as a documented system-level case study rather than as a fully powered hypothesis test.

3.7. Statistical reporting conventions

For offline experiments, reported macro-AUC values are out-of-fold estimates from the file-level GroupKFold procedure. These descriptive comparisons use no significance threshold and no multiple-comparison adjustment. Predictions are first concatenated across the five held-out folds, and macro-AUC is then computed manually as the unweighted mean of per-species `sklearn.metrics.roc_auc_score` values over the 71 species with both positive and negative examples in the bank. No thresholding, class weighting, or taxon weighting is used for AUC. The analyses use Python/scikit-learn as recorded in the released `environment_freeze.txt` file. The stable artifact snapshot is available at <https://github.com/Sonoform-Labs/BirdClef> under tag `v0.1-preprint`; artifact paths, code, configuration notes, and run instructions are summarized in the Code Availability statement and `docs/reproducibility.md`. Fold-level summaries, when available, are used as descriptive uncertainty summaries rather than as independent replicated experiments, because the number of folds

Table 2

Endpoint hierarchy and analysis workflow. OOF = out-of-fold; AUC = area under the ROC curve; SSM = selective state-space model. Prototype presence-purity is the nearest-neighbor class-match fraction for evaluated prototypes. D2-FOCAL is the D2-style head retrained with the 708-window soundscape bank plus 5,090 focal windows from 206 species. The primary deployment endpoint is the single aggregate Kaggle private macro-AUC over the hidden 234-species task. Offline OOF AUC over the 71 covered species is used for development and replacement-head selection, not as the final deployment endpoint. Hidden-test rows are descriptive leaderboard aggregates with no paired confidence intervals, p-values, or covariate adjustment because hidden labels are unavailable.

Analysis step	Data / population	Statistic reported	Purpose / status
Offline bank and folds	708 labelled 5-s soundscape windows from 59 complete 1-min files; 71 covered and 163 offline-absent species; GroupKFold(5) by source file	Fold assignment and covered/absent species lists	Development population and leakage control
Offline replacement sweeps	Same 708-window bank; 71 covered species only	OOF macro-AUC; prototype presence-purity	Development endpoint. D2 is selected by highest OOF AUC; D1 is retained as high-purity comparator
Primary deployment comparison	Fixed ProtoSSMv2+SED core with ProtoSSMv2, Drop, D1 pure, or D2 input-gated prototype-member slot	Single aggregate Kaggle private macro-AUC over 234 species	Primary descriptive endpoint. D2 is compared with ProtoSSMv2 and Drop on private macro-AUC
Exploratory submitted variants	Same fixed deployment core with coverage-gating, re-weighting, no-SSM, or D2-FOCAL intervention	Aggregate public/private Kaggle macro-AUC	Exploratory rescue, sensitivity, or temporal-ablation rows
Coverage diagnostics	Covered (71) vs. offline-absent (163) species groups defined by the offline bank	Descriptive score correlations and variance ratios	Exploratory group summaries, not causal tests
Matched-control study	Separate AudioProtoPNet-style matched-control experiment	Fold-level macro-AUC difference, purity, shortcut rate	Supporting interpretability control outside the deployment testbed

is small and species coverage is incomplete. Hyperparameter sweeps on the offline bank are treated as model-development analyses; they should not be read as a locked, independent model-selection benchmark.

Prototype presence-purity is reported over the set of evaluated prototypes. For the ProtoSSMv2 audit, the nearest-neighbor pool is the 708-window soundscape bank, nearest windows are selected by cosine similarity, null purity is computed by random class reassignment over 1000 draws, and the reported 95% interval uses a percentile bootstrap over prototypes with 3000 draws. These intervals summarize uncertainty over prototypes rather than hidden-test deployment uncertainty. For hidden-test leaderboard results, Kaggle returns only aggregate public/private macro-AUC scores and does not expose per-example or per-species labels. We therefore do not compute paired tests, per-species confidence intervals, or p-values for leaderboard differences. Public and private scores are reported as descriptive system-level outcomes. No significance threshold, sided test, or multiple-comparison correction is used for leaderboard comparisons or exploratory subgroup/rescue analyses.

4. Deployment Testbed

We use a fixed ProtoSSMv2+SED rank-fusion core as the deployment testbed for all replacement experiments. This core contains two active members: the deployed ProtoSSMv2 prototype member and a Perch-distilled SED member. Auxiliary EfficientNet members from the original public pipeline are disabled uniformly across the reported replacement experiments. Table 8 contains prototype-member replacements, a temporal-module ablation, and one fusion-weight change; each row uses the same fixed ProtoSSMv2+SED core except for the named intervention.

Each member’s scores are converted to per-species percentile ranks and then weighted-summed. For member m , species c , raw score $s_c^{(m)}$, rank-percentile score $r_c^{(m)}$, and fusion weight w_m , the final fused

Table 3

What is public versus ours. The deployed pipeline is a fixed, public testbed; our contribution is the controlled replacement of its prototype member and the analysis around it. D1 denotes the pure multi-prototype replacement head; D2 denotes the input-gated high-offline-AUC replacement head; eco. priors denotes empirical-Bayes ecological priors.

Component	Source	Role in this study
Perch v2 embeddings / logits	public model [6]	fixed testbed
ProtoSSMv2 prototype member	public notebook [7]	fixed testbed (replaced)
Perch-distilled SED member	public notebook [7]	fixed testbed
Rank fusion + eco. priors	public notebook [7]	fixed testbed
D1 / D2 / static-gate heads	this work	intervention
Controlled replacement + analysis	this work	contribution
Matched-control study (App. A)	this work	contribution

score is

$$r_c^{(m)} = \text{rankpercentile}(s_c^{(m)}), \quad S_c = \sum_m w_m r_c^{(m)}.$$

Rank-space blending is natural for macro-AUC because the metric depends only on within-species ordering. The deployed ProtoSSMv2+SED core scores 0.942 private macro-AUC on the hidden test. Since hidden labels are not released, this score is used only as the deployment reference for descriptive replacement comparisons.

The prototype member, ProtoSSMv2 [7], uses one class-specific prototype per species, projected to a 320-dimensional space. It computes cosine similarity between Perch-derived features and class prototypes, applies positive-temperature scaling via softplus, and blends prototype scores with Perch logits using a learned per-class fusion gate $\gamma_c = \sigma(\alpha_c)$. A bidirectional residual selective state-space model [16, 17] aggregates predictions across the 12 temporal windows in each one-minute soundscape file.

The SED model uses an EfficientNet [18] backbone distilled from Perch embeddings (MSE loss), producing clip-level and frame-level logits combined as $p = 0.5 \cdot \sigma(l_{\text{clip}}) + 0.5 \cdot \sigma(\max_t l_{\text{frame}}(t))$, averaged across 5 folds with Gaussian smoothing ($\sigma=0.65$).

Post-processing includes empirical-Bayes ecological priors (site/hour shrinkage estimators with circular-Gaussian hour smoothing, $\sigma=1.5$ hours) and rank-active methods (taxonomy smoothing, file-level max pooling, top-2 averaging, and Δ -smoothing). We verified that per-class temperature scaling and isotonic thresholding are rank-inert (0.00 rank change), confirming they cannot affect AUC.

We do not claim novelty for the base pipeline; it is used as a fixed deployment testbed. Our contribution is the controlled replacement of its prototype member and the analysis around that replacement. Table 3 states what is public and what is ours.

5. Prototype Head Design and Offline Evaluation

5.1. Replacement-head setup

We design and train replacement prototype classification heads on frozen Perch v2 embeddings (1,536-d). For an input window x , let $z(x)$ denote the frozen Perch embedding and $\ell_c^{\text{Perch}}(x)$ denote the Perch logit for species c when available. Each prototype head contains one or more learned prototypes $p_{c,k}$ assigned to species c . With normalized embeddings and prototypes, the prototype activation is

$$a_{c,k}(x) = \left\langle \frac{z(x)}{\|z(x)\|}, \frac{p_{c,k}}{\|p_{c,k}\|} \right\rangle, \quad a_c(x) = \max_k a_{c,k}(x).$$

The prototype logit is then

$$h_c(x) = \text{softplus}(\eta_c) a_c(x) + b_c,$$

where η_c is the learnable temperature parameter and b_c is a per-class bias. For pure prototype heads, $h_c(x)$ is the class score. For fusion heads, the prototype logit is combined with the Perch logit through a convex gate,

$$q_c(x) = \gamma_c(x)h_c(x) + (1 - \gamma_c(x))\ell_c^{\text{Perch}}(x).$$

The static-gate head uses $\gamma_c = \sigma(\alpha_c)$, while D2 uses an input-dependent gate $\gamma_c(x)$. D1 denotes the pure multi-prototype replacement head with interpretability losses; D2 denotes the input-gated high-offline-AUC replacement head.

Training uses FocalBCE loss [19], AdamW [20], and cosine annealing over 60 epochs. The committed primary export scripts initialize learned prototypes in the frozen 1,536-d embedding space with small random normal weights, initialize temperatures to 5.0 and biases to zero, use AdamW with learning rate 10^{-3} and weight decay 10^{-4} , apply cosine annealing with $T_{\text{max}} = 60$, use full-batch optimization on the 708-window bank, clip gradients at 1.0, and do not use early stopping. D1 uses focal loss plus cluster and separation losses with weights 0.8 and 0.08; D2 uses the input-gated focal objective without the interpretability losses. When interpretability losses are active, the training objective is

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{FocalBCE}} + \lambda_{\text{clust}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{clust}} + \lambda_{\text{sep}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{sep}}.$$

Using cosine distance $d(u, p) = 1 - \langle u/\|u\|, p/\|p\| \rangle$, the cluster loss pulls each prototype toward windows containing its assigned class, while the separation loss penalizes closeness to confirmed-absent windows for that class. The multi-label-aware separation variant changes only the negative set used by \mathcal{L}_{sep} : in multi-species windows, co-occurring positive species are not treated as negatives for one another.

5.2. Training folds and model selection

For the primary replacement heads and the offline sweeps, each GroupKFold split is trained independently on four file groups and evaluated on the held-out file group. Out-of-fold predictions are concatenated across folds before computing macro-AUC over the 71 covered species. The offline design sweeps are model-development analyses on the same local bank: D2 was selected as the high-offline-AUC replacement head, while D1 was selected as the high-purity pure-prototype comparison. Because the same local bank guided design choices, the offline frontier should be interpreted as a descriptive development result rather than as a completely independent final test. The hidden-test replacement submissions provide the separate deployment check, but those scores are also descriptive because hidden labels are unavailable.

Perch embeddings are strongly species-discriminative: a t-SNE projection of focal recordings (Figure 2) shows that different species occupy well-separated regions of the embedding space, which is what makes a single prototype per species a viable starting point.

Prototype **presence-purity** is defined as: for each prototype, whether the nearest soundscape window in the 708-window bank (by cosine similarity) contains the prototype’s assigned class. For prototype set \mathcal{P} , assigned class $c(p)$, and nearest window x_p^* , we compute

$$\text{purity} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}|} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \mathbf{1}\{y_{c(p)}(x_p^*) = 1\}.$$

5.3. Deployed head audit

Before building new heads, we audited the deployed ProtoSSMv2 [7] to establish the reference we aim to match.

Architecture. ProtoSSMv2 uses 234 class-specific prototypes (one per species, 320-d after internal projection), a positive-temperature diagonal cosine readout, a per-class fusion gate $\gamma_c = \sigma(\alpha_c)$, and a bidirectional residual SSM [16].

Perch embedding space: focal recordings cluster by species

Figure 2: Qualitative t-SNE projection of frozen Perch v2 embeddings for focal recordings of twelve representative species; each point is one focal recording window and labels use the competition species codes. Axes are arbitrary t-SNE coordinates (t-SNE 1 and t-SNE 2), not calibrated acoustic distances. The plot is a representation diagnostic only and is not used as a quantitative endpoint; t-SNE layout choices do not enter any reported AUC or purity metric. Prototype-head training and evaluation use the labelled multi-species soundscape bank described in Section 7.

Table 4

ProtoSSMv2 fusion gate γ by taxon. Values are descriptive means and standard deviations over species in each taxon; Reptilia contains one target species, so no standard deviation is reported. The gate is nearly uniform across taxa and Perch-mapping status in this trained model.

Taxon	Mean γ	Std
Amphibia	0.497	0.003
Aves	0.501	0.003
Insecta	0.503	0.003
Mammalia	0.499	0.002
Reptilia	0.501	–

Fusion gate analysis. The learned gate values are nearly constant: $\gamma \approx 0.50$ across all 234 species and all taxa (global std 0.003, range [0.493, 0.507]). Table 4 summarizes the taxon-level means. In this trained run, the gate does not show a visible coverage- or taxon-specific allocation between prototype scores and Perch logits. We treat this as a descriptive audit result rather than as a test of alternative gate training recipes.

Prototype validity. ProtoSSMv2’s prototype purity is 0.789 [95% CI 0.69–0.87], compared with a permutation-null mean of 0.024 ± 0.018 . The per-taxon purity estimates are Insecta 0.96, Amphibia 0.88, and Aves 0.64 (Mammalia 0.33, $n=3$; Reptilia 0.00, $n=1$; both reported only as small- n values); see Figure 3.

A sample-composition check gives descriptive, non-inferential diagnostics. Purity has a positive correlation with log-sample-count (Spearman $\rho = 0.30$), and a logistic regression with the log-count covariate gives taxon coefficients of Insecta +1.40 and Aves -0.71 relative to Amphibia. We do not use

Figure 3: Per-taxon prototype presence-purity for AudioProtoPNet (matched-control study, Appendix A; ConvNeXt backbone) and ProtoSSMv2 (Perch embeddings). Presence-purity is a unitless nearest-neighbor class-match fraction over evaluated prototypes. Bars are descriptive point estimates; taxon-level uncertainty intervals are not shown. ProtoSSMv2 has one class prototype per target species, but small-taxon estimates should be read cautiously (Mammalia $n=3$, Reptilia $n=1$ in the displayed audit). “Coverage-limited” indicates that the AudioProtoPNet insect estimate uses only 3 of 28 insect species with enough clean clips for the matched-control purity calculation. The two systems differ in backbone, training data, and prototype granularity, so the contrast is descriptive only.

this correlation or regression as a formal taxon-comparison test and do not report p-values for it. These coefficients are included only as descriptive diagnostics because the taxon groups differ in sample size, acoustic structure, and representation quality.

5.4. The offline frontier

Unless otherwise stated, the results in Sections 6–7 and in the offline frontier below are descriptive point estimates. Offline values are out-of-fold (OOF) macro-AUC or prototype-purity summaries computed on the 708-window bank over the 71 covered species. Hidden-test values are single aggregate Kaggle public/private macro-AUC scores over the 234-species deployment task; hidden labels are unavailable, so paired confidence intervals, per-species tests, and p-values are not reported for leaderboard comparisons.

This subsection reports OOF macro-AUC and prototype presence-purity for replacement-head development on the 71 covered species.

Table 5

Offline build-up and reference rows on frozen Perch embeddings. Perch is the frozen Perch-v2 logit/embedding baseline; the linear probe is a sigmoid classifier on frozen Perch embeddings; D1 is the high-purity 3-prototype reference head; D2 is the input-gated high-OOF-AUC replacement head. AUC is covered-species OOF macro-AUC over the 71 evaluable species. Pur. is unitless prototype presence-purity. In the sequential build-up block, Δ AUC and Δ Pur. are changes from the row immediately above; for the non-sequential reference rows, “ref.” means no sequential delta is defined. “n/a” means the metric is not applicable to a non-prototype baseline. Bold marks the largest measured value among applicable rows in each metric column; ties are retained.

#	Config	AUC	Δ AUC	Pur.	Δ Pur.
<i>Non-prototype baselines</i>					
–	Perch alone	.739	ref.	n/a	n/a
1	Linear probe	.766	+0.027	n/a	n/a
<i>Sequential 1-prototype build-up</i>					
2	1-proto, no loss	.762	–.004	.690	ref.
3	+ cluster	.604	–.158	.944	+0.254
4	+ separation	.605	+0.001	.958	+0.014
5	+ static gate	.742	+0.137	.958	.000
6	+ input gate (D2)	.830	+0.088	.437	–.521
<i>Non-sequential prototype reference rows</i>					
7	3-proto+loss (D1)	.606	ref.	.958	ref.
–	Deployed ProtoSSMv2	.803	ref.	.790	ref.

The offline sweep shows a trade-off between OOF macro-AUC and prototype presence-purity (Table 5; Figure 4). The statistics are covered-species OOF macro-AUC and unitless nearest-neighbor purity. Three descriptive patterns define the frontier:

Cluster loss gives the largest observed purity increase. Adding cluster loss (rows 2→3) changes purity by +0.254 and AUC by –0.158. This is the largest single-row change in Table 5. Separation loss adds +0.014 purity (rows 3→4). A multi-label-aware separation variant performs similarly to standard separation (AUC 0.603 vs. 0.605). The separate D1 reference row with three prototypes per class has AUC .606 and purity .958.

The input-dependent gate changes the AUC–purity balance. Replacing the static gate with the selected input-dependent D2 gate (rows 5→6) changes AUC by +0.088 and purity by –0.521. The selected D2 row in Table 5 is therefore the high-OOF-AUC input-gated configuration (.830 AUC, .437 purity). Loss-retaining gated ablations from the broader development sweep did not reach D2-level AUC, so the frontier separates the high-purity static-gate region from the high-AUC D2 region. No gated configuration in this sweep has both D2-level AUC and row-5-level purity.

Row 5 retains high purity at Perch-level AUC. The static-gate row with cluster and separation losses (row 5) has .742 AUC and .958 purity. Its AUC is close to the Perch-alone baseline (.739), below D2 (.830), and below deployed ProtoSSMv2 on the same offline endpoint (.803).

5.5. Design sweeps

This subsection reports descriptive within-family sweep deltas on the offline bank. The statistics are changes in covered-species OOF macro-AUC and prototype presence-purity relative to the family baseline named in Table 6.

Table 6 shows small AUC changes from prototype-count sweeps. For the pure-prototype family, increasing K changes AUC by at most +0.002 from its stated baseline. At $K=10$, purity changes by

Figure 4: Offline interpretability-accuracy frontier for the configurations in Table 5. The x-axis should be read as covered-species OOF macro-AUC over 71 species; the y-axis is unitless prototype presence-purity. D1 is the high-purity pure-prototype replacement head, and D2 is the input-gated high-offline-AUC replacement head. Reference lines, when shown, mark the Perch-alone and linear-probe AUC baselines. Points are descriptive offline estimates; no fold-level error bars are shown.

Table 6

Design sweeps within two head families. For the pure-prototype family, Δ values are relative to the cluster+separation baseline in Table 5 (AUC .605, purity .958). For the gated-head family, Δ values are relative to D2 input-gated in Table 5 (AUC .830, purity .437). Δ AUC and Δ Pur. are within-family differences from the stated baseline; “n.m.” indicates that purity was not measured for that sweep.

Family	Sweep	Variant	Δ AUC	Δ Pur.
Pure-proto	Prototype count K	$K=3$	+0.001	.000
Pure-proto	Prototype count K	$K=10$	+0.002	-.518
Pure-proto	Projection	linear 320-d	+0.042	.000
Pure-proto	Separation loss	multi-label	-.002	.000
Gated head	Prototype count K	$K=3$	+0.003	+0.105
Gated head	Prototype count K	$K=5$	+0.006	+0.169
Gated head	Epochs	25 (peak)	+0.018	n.m.
Gated head	Gate type	static scalar	-.088	+0.521

-0.518. For the gated-head family, $K=5$ changes AUC by +0.006 and purity by +0.169 relative to the D2 baseline.

Projection and training-length sweeps show larger offline AUC changes. A linear 320-d projection changes pure-prototype AUC by +0.042 with no measured purity change. The D2 epoch sweep reaches its largest observed offline AUC at 25 epochs. Temporal smoothing across windows gives no positive

Table 7

Per-taxon covered-species OOF macro-AUC for key configurations. Values are descriptive out-of-fold macro-AUC estimates over species with positives in the 708-window bank; numbers in parentheses are covered species counts. Mammalia and Reptilia are omitted as separate rows because of very small covered-species counts but are included in All. Bold indicates the highest value in each row.

Taxon	Linear	D2 (gated)	D1 (pure)
Aves (25)	.712	.804	.552
Amphibia (17)	.799	.884	.687
Insecta (25)	.820	.827	.619
All (71)	.766	.830	.606

Table 8

Leaderboard evaluation. Each row applies the named prototype-member replacement, temporal ablation, or fusion-weight change inside the same deployed Proto+SED core and is scored on the hidden test. Auxiliary CNN members are disabled uniformly. Off. is the covered-species out-of-fold macro-AUC endpoint when available; Pub. and Priv. are aggregate Kaggle public/private hidden-test macro-AUC scores; Δ is Priv. minus the ProtoSSMv2 private baseline. D1 is the pure prototype head; D2 is the input-gated head; no-SSM bypasses the deployed head’s SSM-based temporal module; cov-gated uses prototype scores only for species covered by the offline bank; Drop uses raw Perch logits in place of the prototype member. Leaderboard values are descriptive aggregate outputs, not formal statistical-test estimates.

Head	Off.	Pub.	Priv.	Δ
ProtoSSMv2	.803	.949	.942	–
ProtoSSMv2 no-SSM	–	.948	.941	–.001
D1 cov-gated	.606	.944	.940	–.003
ProtoSSMv2 cov-g.	.803	.946	.940	–.003
D2 re-weighted	.830	.942	.939	–.003
Drop (Perch)	.739	.945	.939	–.003
D1 pure	.606	.938	.938	–.004
D2 cov-gated	.830	.944	.938	–.005
D2 input-gated	.830	.941	.937	–.005
D2-FOCAL	–	.939	.935	–.007

change in this sweep.

5.6. Per-taxon accuracy

This subsection reports descriptive per-taxon OOF macro-AUC over the covered species in the offline bank. The population is limited to taxa with enough covered species for a row-level summary.

D2 is the highest-AUC configuration in each reported taxon row (Table 7). Relative to the linear probe, D2 changes AUC by +0.092 on Aves, +0.085 on Amphibia, and +0.007 on Insecta. D1 is below the linear probe in each reported taxon row. This per-taxon AUC pattern differs from the purity pattern in Figure 3, where Insecta has the highest ProtoSSMv2 purity point estimate.

6. Hidden-Test Replacement Results

This section reports the primary deployment check. The statistic is the single aggregate Kaggle private macro-AUC over the hidden 234-species task for each submitted full-system variant. These comparisons are descriptive point estimates; hidden labels are unavailable for paired confidence intervals, per-species tests, or p-values. For this descriptive check, the offline-selected D2 replacement is compared against two private-macro-AUC references: the deployed ProtoSSMv2 row and the raw-Perch Drop row.

Table 9 summarizes the primary hidden-test comparison, where the deployed ProtoSSMv2 member scored highest.

Table 9

Primary replacement summary. This table separates the main deployment comparison from exploratory rescue variants. Offline AUC is the covered-species out-of-fold (OOF) macro-AUC endpoint; Private AUC is the aggregate Kaggle private hidden-test macro-AUC endpoint. Values are descriptive system-level outcomes; hidden labels are unavailable for paired confidence intervals or p-values.

System	Offline AUC	Private AUC	Role
ProtoSSMv2	.803	.942	deployed reference
ProtoSSMv2 no-SSM	–	.941	temporal-module ablation
Drop (Perch)	.739	.939	no-prototype baseline
D1 pure	.606	.938	high-purity replacement
D2 input-gated	.830	.937	high-offline-AUC replacement

Table 10

D2 gate and score diagnostics split by offline coverage group. Covered species are the 71 species with at least one positive label in the 708-window bank; absent species are the remaining 163 target species with zero positives in that bank. $\rho(\text{D2, Perch})$ is the within-group Spearman correlation over species between D2 and Perch scores. Var. ratio is the within-group variance of D2 scores divided by the within-group variance of Perch scores. These diagnostics are descriptive and not used as formal tests.

Species group	Mean γ	$\rho(\text{D2, Perch})$	Var. ratio
Covered (71)	0.779	0.319	0.485
Absent (163)	0.767	0.276	0.347

The offline selected D2 replacement is below both private-macro-AUC references in the hidden-test comparison. D2 is selected by the covered-species offline endpoint, but its private macro-AUC is lower than the deployed ProtoSSMv2 row and the raw-Perch Drop row. D1 has a lower offline AUC than D2 and a slightly higher private score. These score gaps are reported as descriptive system-level differences (Section 10).

The exploratory rows in Table 8 remain below the deployed ProtoSSMv2 row. Coverage-gated and re-weighted rows fall between the deployed reference and the primary replacements. The no-SSM row is a separate temporal-module ablation; its private score is below ProtoSSMv2 and above Drop, D1, and D2. Section 7 reports the exploratory diagnostics.

7. Exploratory Diagnostics

This section reports exploratory diagnostics after the primary hidden-test replacement comparison. Each diagnostic is a descriptive point estimate or group summary, not an inferential decomposition of cause. The diagnostics cover offline-absent species, coverage-gating controls, a temporal-module ablation, and a broad-training sensitivity experiment.

7.1. Diagnostic: offline-absent species

D2 has lower score correlation and lower score-variance ratio on offline-absent species than on covered species. The comparison uses two groups defined by the 708-window bank: 71 covered species and 163 offline-absent species. Table 10 reports the group summaries.

The input-dependent gate has similar mean values in the two groups. In contrast, the D2/Perch variance ratio is lower for absent species than for covered species. These values are descriptive diagnostics over species groups; they are not formal tests of a mechanism.

Figure 5: Offline out-of-fold (OOF) macro-AUC versus aggregate Kaggle private hidden-test macro-AUC for submitted variants with an offline OOF endpoint. OOF macro-AUC is computed only over the 71 covered species in the local bank; private AUC is a single aggregate Kaggle score over the hidden 234-species task. Marker families identify the deployed ProtoSSMv2 reference, the raw-Perch Drop baseline, the primary author-built heads (D1 pure and D2 input-gated), and exploratory rescue variants. Rescue markers denote coverage-gated variants, where prototype scores are used only for the 71 offline-covered species, and the D2 re-weighted variant, where the prototype-fusion weight is reduced. The no-SSM temporal ablation is omitted because it has no separately computed offline OOF endpoint. The y-axis is zoomed for ordering only; no hidden-label confidence intervals or p-values are available.

7.2. Control 1: Coverage-gating

Coverage-gating raises both author-built replacement rows but does not reach the deployed ProtoSSMv2 score. The statistic is single aggregate private macro-AUC for the hidden 234-species task.

D1 changes from 0.938 to 0.940 (+0.002), and D2 changes from 0.937 to 0.938 (+0.001). Both rows remain close to the raw-Perch Drop baseline (≈ 0.939). Neither coverage-gated row matches the deployed head. The coverage-gating rule is defined in Table 8’s caption and in the released artifacts.

7.3. Control 2: Temporal ablation

Bypassing the deployed head’s SSM-based temporal module lowers its private macro-AUC but leaves it above the primary replacements. The statistic is single aggregate private macro-AUC for the hidden 234-species task.

The no-SSM variant has private macro-AUC 0.94089, compared with 0.94218 for the deployed reference (Table 8). It is above the raw-Perch Drop baseline and above both primary replacement heads. This contrast reports the observed score after bypassing one temporal module; it does not apportion the remaining difference among architecture, capacity, training procedure, or full-label-space behavior.

Figure 6: Aggregate Kaggle private hidden-test macro-AUC for all ten submitted system variants. D1 is the high-purity pure-prototype replacement head; D2 is the input-gated high-offline-AUC replacement head; cov-gated means prototype scores are used only for the 71 offline-covered species; re-weighted means the prototype-fusion weight is reduced; Drop replaces the prototype member with raw Perch logits; no-SSM bypasses the deployed head’s selective state-space model (SSM) temporal module; D2-FOCAL is the D2-style head retrained with focal windows plus the soundscape bank. Values are single aggregate private leaderboard scores over the hidden 234-species task, not paired statistical estimates. Bar labels are rounded for display; exact submitted values are tabulated in Table 8 and the released leaderboard summary. The y-axis is zoomed to show ordering, so absolute score gaps are visually amplified and should be read as small descriptive differences.

7.4. Control 3: Deployed-head coverage-gating

Coverage-gating the deployed ProtoSSMv2 itself changes the private score from 0.942 to 0.940 when the deployed prototype member is restricted to covered species. A descriptive decomposition of ProtoSSMv2’s +0.003 private-score difference relative to raw Perch gives +0.0003 on covered species and +0.0026 on offline-absent species. These calculations are descriptive diagnostics only. They do not apportion causal effects. The comparison to lower-capacity replacement heads remains confounded by architecture, capacity, and training procedure (Section 10).

7.5. Broad-training sensitivity experiment

D2-FOCAL has the lowest private score among the evaluated variants. The statistic is single aggregate private macro-AUC for the hidden 234-species task.

D2-FOCAL uses the gated head trained on a combined bank: the 708 soundscape windows plus 5,090 focal windows spanning 206 species. Its observed private score is 0.935. In this focal-heavy recipe, the combined-bank head scores below the other evaluated variants. We tested only one recipe; balanced focal/soundscape sampling, domain weighting, and target-distribution pseudo-labeling remain untested.

7.6. Summary

The exploratory diagnostics do not identify a single isolated cause. Coverage-gating changes the replacement rows but leaves them below the deployed reference. The no-SSM ablation lowers the deployed score while leaving it above both primary replacements. The tested broad off-domain training recipe has the lowest private score among the evaluated rows.

8. Supporting Study: Prototype Interpretability in a Controlled Setting

This auxiliary study checks whether the deployment reversal should be read as a general failure of prototype explanations. It should not be read as a second deployment experiment. In a cleaner single-backbone setting, we compare an AudioProtoPNet-style prototype head [10] with an otherwise identical sigmoid baseline on a shared ConvNeXt-Base backbone. The reported effect size is prototype minus sigmoid macro-AUC across the same five folds; uncertainty is summarized by cross-fold standard error and by a paired instance bootstrap with 2000 resamples (Appendix A). The prototype head has little observed macro-AUC cost ($\Delta = -0.007$, 95% CI spanning zero), while its avian prototypes are strongly class-pure (0.951 versus a 0.006 random-prototype null) and avoid low-energy shortcut patches.

This auxiliary result provides a counterpoint to a blanket “prototypes fail” interpretation. In this cleaner matched-control setting, the prototype head remains accuracy-competitive and its avian prototypes are class-pure under the reported nearest-neighbor audit. A compact version of the matched-control study is provided in Appendix A.

9. Discussion

Direct finding. This paper is a scoped, descriptive system-level case study rather than a universal claim about prototype models. The main observed result is an offline-to-deployment model-selection failure under controlled replacement. Inside the fixed ProtoSSMv2+SED core, the deployed prototype member remains best on the hidden private split, while both primary author-built replacement heads fall below the raw-Perch drop baseline. This result is descriptive rather than inferential, because hidden-test labels are unavailable for paired testing, but it is the central empirical observation of the study.

Interpretation: partial-label evaluation exposes unmeasured failure modes. The proposed explanation is that the offline bank evaluates only the 71 species with positives in the labelled soundscape bank, while the deployment system must score the broader 234-species target space. The exploratory mechanism diagnostics are consistent with this interpretation in two ways. First, D2 has lower Perch-score correlation and lower score-variance ratio on species absent from the offline bank than on covered species. Second, coverage-gating the author-built heads improves hidden-test performance, which is consistent with deployment loss from using prototype scores for species with no offline positives. These findings do not prove that label coverage is the only mechanism; rather, they show that partial-label evaluation can hide damage on classes it never evaluates.

Temporal aggregation and architecture are partial contributors. The no-SSM ablation sharpens the mechanism claim. Removing the deployed head’s temporal module reduces private macro-AUC from 0.94218 to 0.94089; this is the observed score after bypassing the temporal module. However, the ablated deployed head still scores above both primary replacement heads and the raw-Perch drop baseline. The deployment gap is therefore treated as multi-causal: coverage handling, temporal aggregation, and remaining architectural differences all remain plausible contributors to the final deployment ordering. The present evidence supports partial-label blindness as a failure mode, but it does not isolate every architectural factor in ProtoSSMv2.

Interpretable components must be evaluated as deployed components. The matched-control study (Appendix A) shows that prototype explanations can be class-pure and call-focused in a cleaner single-backbone setting. That result narrows the interpretation of the main failure: the problem is not that prototype explanations are inherently invalid, but that a locally interpretable component can still reduce deployment performance when it is selected using an incomplete offline label space. For systems like BirdCLEF+ 2026, interpretability and deployment value are therefore separate endpoints. A component can be more interpretable, or better on the covered offline bank, without improving the full system.

Taxon gradients are suggestive, not causal evidence. AudioProtoPNet’s bird-centric pre-training produces a bird-clean purity gradient, while ProtoSSMv2’s soundscape-trained Perch-based prototypes are cleaner for insects. This contrast is consistent with the idea that prototype validity depends on training domain and acoustic distinctiveness. However, the comparison is confounded by backbone, embedding space, training data, and prototype granularity. We therefore treat the opposite taxon gradients as hypothesis-generating rather than as evidence for a causal taxon- or domain-level mechanism.

Practical recommendations. Three recommendations follow directly from the observed replacement results. First, report label coverage for any offline component benchmark; otherwise, offline gains may be driven by a subset of classes that does not represent deployment. Second, evaluate interpretable components inside the full system at least once, because component-level metrics do not capture interactions with rank fusion, foundation-model logits, or post-processing. Third, when a component is trained on a subset of the deployment label space, include absent-class diagnostics or coverage-gated controls to check whether the component damages classes the offline metric cannot score. The first recommendation follows from the 71/234 offline coverage gap, the second from the hidden-test replacement comparison, and the third from the coverage-gating diagnostics. These recommendations are scoped to BirdCLEF-style multi-label bioacoustic systems and should be tested in additional pipelines.

Negative results. Several null or adverse results constrain the interpretation of the study. The multi-label-aware separation loss performs similarly to standard separation. ProtoSSMv2’s per-class gate remains nearly uniform rather than learning an obvious coverage-aware allocation. Increasing prototype count improves neither pure-head accuracy nor deployment performance. Broad focal-heavy training reduces deployment performance in the tested recipe. Finally, the initial expectation that the high-offline-AUC D2 head would transfer best to the leaderboard does not hold. Together, these results provide no evidence that the observed deployment mismatch is fixed by a single local design change.

10. Limitations

This section separates the validity limits attached to each major result. The hidden-test replacement comparison supports a descriptive deployment ordering for this submitted system, not a paired inferential claim. The no-SSM ablation supports only the score observed after bypassing one temporal module, not a complete causal attribution of the deployment gap. The prototype-purity analyses support a nearest-neighbor property of prototypes, not full human-validated interpretability.

10.1. Statistical conclusion validity

The offline evaluation uses 708 labelled soundscape windows from 59 files and covers only 71 of 234 target species. This limits precision: fold-level uncertainty is wide, and the offline D2–ProtoSSMv2 difference should be interpreted descriptively rather than as a statistically secure ordering. The hidden-test replacement results are also descriptive. Kaggle returns one aggregate public score and one aggregate private score per submission, and hidden labels are unavailable, so we cannot compute paired tests, per-species confidence intervals, or submission-level p-values. The public and private splits are not

independent replications; they are two partitions of the same hidden evaluation source. For these reasons, we present the leaderboard reversal as a documented case study in this pipeline rather than as a statistically established universal effect.

10.2. Internal validity

The controlled replacement design holds the ProtoSSMv2+SED core fixed and changes only the prototype member artifact, which reduces system-level confounding. However, the replacement heads and the deployed ProtoSSMv2 member still differ in architecture, capacity, training procedure, and temporal structure. The no-SSM ablation reports a 0.0013 private macro-AUC drop after bypassing the deployed temporal module, but it does not isolate all non-temporal architectural differences. The ablated deployed head still outperforms the raw-Perch drop baseline and both primary replacement heads, so the remaining advantage is confounded with capacity, fusion design, and other implementation choices. A fully matched causal test would require training heads with matched capacity and identical temporal aggregation under the same data regime.

10.3. Construct validity

Presence-purity is a weak proxy for interpretability in multi-label soundscapes. It verifies only that the nearest window contains the assigned class; it does not prove that the prototype matched the target call rather than a co-occurring species, background texture, recording condition, or correlated acoustic event. The matched-control AudioProtoPNet study uses a stronger shortcut-rate check based on call energy, but that analysis is performed in a cleaner supporting setting rather than in the full deployed ProtoSSMv2 system. Future interpretability validation should pair presence-purity with nearest-neighbor spectrogram panels, audio inspection, energy-overlap checks, and ideally expert review.

10.4. External validity

The results come from one BirdCLEF+ 2026 deployment pipeline and one competition hidden test. The central lesson is therefore scoped: partial-label offline evaluation can favor an interpretable component that underperforms after full-system deployment in this BirdCLEF-style system. We do not claim that prototype heads generally fail, that temporal aggregation is always necessary, or that the same deployment reversal will occur in other bioacoustic datasets. The broad-training result is also limited: D2-FOCAL used one focal-heavy recipe in which 5,090 focal windows outweighed 708 on-domain soundscape windows. Balanced focal/soundscape sampling, domain weighting, pseudo-labeling on target soundscapes, and species-held-out validation remain untested.

10.5. Supporting-study limitations

The matched-control AudioProtoPNet study uses 6 training epochs, whereas the original AudioProtoPNet training used 20. Longer training could reveal accuracy differences not captured here, especially for prototype regularization losses that may require more time to shape the latent space. This limitation affects only the supporting AudioProtoPNet control and not the main ProtoSSMv2+SED replacement experiments. The comparison between AudioProtoPNet and the Perch-based heads is also confounded by backbone, embedding space, training data, and prototype granularity. The opposite taxon gradients are therefore suggestive, not causal evidence.

10.6. Reproducibility and artifact limits

The deployment testbed is adopted unchanged from public Kaggle notebooks [7]; only the replacement prototype heads and analyses are author-designed. The repository linked below documents the replacement-head code, figure scripts, result tables, no-SSM builder, coverage lists, D2-FOCAL

provenance, and deployment-substitution workflow. However, hidden-test labels are not public, and the deployed base notebook is inherited from the public Kaggle reference pipeline, so leaderboard scores cannot be recomputed from labels outside the Kaggle evaluation system. The artifact release therefore separates reproducible offline analyses and artifact-generation scripts from leaderboard rows that can only be verified through the original submission environment.

11. Future Work

Future work should separate the factors examined above in a prioritized sequence rather than simply adding more replacement heads. First, a matched-capacity temporal ablation should compare four conditions: deployed ProtoSSMv2, ProtoSSMv2 without temporal aggregation, an author-built head with matched capacity but no temporal aggregation, and the same author-built head with the deployed temporal aggregator. This would separate temporal structure from capacity and fusion design.

Second, broader training should be revisited with controlled domain balance rather than the focal-heavy D2-FOCAL recipe. The most direct follow-up is a small grid over focal/soundscape sampling ratios, with species-held-out validation and a target-soundscape pseudo-labeling condition. This would test whether broader species coverage helps once focal recordings no longer swamp on-domain soundscapes.

Third, interpretability validation should move beyond presence-purity. For each prototype family, nearest-neighbor spectrogram and audio panels should be paired with energy-overlap or call-localization checks, and a small expert-reviewed subset would help distinguish target-call matches from co-occurrence or background matches.

Fourth, the partial-label evaluation failure should be replicated in other BirdCLEF-style systems. The key replication test is whether a component selected on a partially covered offline bank also damages absent or weakly covered classes after system-level deployment. If the same pattern appears across backbones, teams, or years, the result would support a general evaluation warning rather than a single-pipeline case study.

12. Conclusion

We used a fixed 234-species bioacoustic deployment testbed to evaluate whether prototype components selected on a partially covered offline soundscape bank transfer to full-system deployment. The answer in this case is no: the highest-offline-AUC replacement head did not improve the deployed system, while the original temporally aggregated prototype member remained best on the hidden test.

The exploratory diagnostics are compatible with label-space coverage as one contributor. The offline bank evaluates only 71 of 234 species, and the replacement heads reduce performance on species absent from that bank. A no-SSM ablation shows a score change after removing temporal aggregation, but the ablated deployed head still scores above the simpler replacements, so the gap is not limited to the temporal module alone.

The scoped lesson is that interpretability and deployment utility are different questions. A prototype component may be plausible, accurate, or interpretable under an offline endpoint while still scoring lower after full-system deployment when the offline labels cover only part of the deployment label space. For bioacoustic systems with partial offline labels, component evaluations should report label coverage, behavior on absent classes, and at least one system-level replacement test rather than relying on the partial offline endpoint alone.

Code Availability

Code, result summaries, figure-generation scripts, and reproducibility artifacts are available at <https://github.com/Sonoform-Labs/BirdClef>. The preprint artifact snapshot is tagged as v0.1-preprint at commit 9dad38f2678c39cc7e5c6c08695606f3d04bed25. The repository includes the no-SSM

ablation builder (`src/kaggle_inference/build_nossm.py`), replacement-head training and export code (`src/part2_perch_heads/`), figure-generation scripts (`src/figures/`), leaderboard and offline result summaries (`results/`), species-coverage lists, D2-FOCAL provenance, an environment record (`environment_freeze.txt`), and reproducibility notes (`docs/reproducibility.md`). Hidden-test labels are not public, so private leaderboard AUC values cannot be independently recomputed from labels; they are recorded as Kaggle leaderboard outputs.

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A. AudioProtoPNet Matched-Control Study

We include a small matched-control study to check whether the main deployment failure should be interpreted as a general failure of prototype explanations. We compare an AudioProtoPNet-style prototype head [10], implemented following the official BirdSet repository,⁴ against a sigmoid classification head on the same ConvNeXt-Base backbone pretrained on BirdSet-XCL [21, 11]. Both models use the same folds, input representation, optimizer, augmentations, and evaluation protocol; only the classification head differs.

The prototype head is accuracy-competitive with the sigmoid baseline. Across five folds, the macro-AUC difference is -0.007 ± 0.006 (prototype minus sigmoid), where the uncertainty is the cross-fold standard error. A paired instance bootstrap with 2000 resamples gives confidence intervals spanning zero. The only consistent cost appears for Aves (-0.011 ± 0.001), while Amphibia and Insecta have noisy fold-level deltas that are not distinguishable from zero.

To test prototype validity, we project each prototype to its nearest patch in a clean single-species pool of focal recordings and single-species soundscape windows. We measure **purity**, the fraction of prototypes whose nearest patch belongs to their own class, and **shortcut rate**, the fraction whose nearest patch falls in the bottom-energy region. Avian prototypes are strongly class-pure (0.951 versus a 0.006 random-prototype null) and avoid low-energy shortcut patches. Amphibian prototypes are moderately pure (0.562) but less consistently call-focused. Insect validity is coverage-limited because only 3 of 28 insect species have sufficient clean clips for this measurement.

These results show that prototype explanations can be class-pure and call-focused in this cleaner single-backbone setting. They do not show that prototype explanations are generally valid in BirdCLEF+ deployment. Therefore, the main paper’s leaderboard reversal should not be read as evidence that prototype interpretability is impossible in bioacoustics. Rather, it supports our narrower claim: prototype components that look valid offline may still fail when selected under partial-label evaluation and deployed inside a full BirdCLEF system.

⁴<https://github.com/DBD-research-group/BirdSet>